

Institutional Annual Research Initiative and QS University Ranking roadmap

Project Report

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Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Maritime University

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Originality Statement

We hereby declare that research work, to the best of our knowledge, contains no contents or materials previously published or written by another person, or substantial proportions of material which have been accepted for the report in any educational institution. Any contribution made to the research by others is explicitly acknowledged in the report.

We also declare that the research work have been carried out using the grant from the Post Graduate Research and Technology Transfer Centre, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Maritime University, Bangladesh.

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17 June 2023

The Director
Post Graduate Research Management and Technology Transfer Centre
Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Maritime University, Bangladesh
Mirpur-12, Dhaka-1216

Subject: Review Report of Research Project on 'Institutional Annual Research Initiative and QS University Ranking roadmap'.

Dear Sir,

1. I have reviewed the research project titled "*Institutional Annual Research Initiative and QS University Ranking roadmap*".
2. The report describes the Institutional Annual Research Initiative (IARI) and the plan for making Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Maritime University (BSMRMU) in Bangladesh a top-tier institution of higher learning. The goals include promoting a research culture, producing influence, cultivating eminent researchers, and improving research abilities. The comprehensive report provides a roadmap for the development of BSMRMU and covers quality education, accreditation, research projects, recruiting quality faculty, researchers, training and development. The objective is to raise the university's standing and create a comprehensive research culture.
3. The significance of accreditation, rating, and ranking in achieving educational excellence in universities is covered in the report. It emphasizes the significance of quality control and the demand for ongoing development. Higher education institutions and academic programs in Bangladesh are accredited by the Bangladesh Accreditation Council (BAC) and Board of Accreditation for Engineering and Technical Education (BAETE), the Institution of Engineers, Bangladesh (IEB). Their process of accreditation is clearly described. It covers also the QS Stars grading system, which rates higher learning institutions according to a number of criteria in order to provide a thorough analysis. These rankings or ratings cover a range of categories, including teaching, research, citations, international collaboration, international faculty, faculty student's ratio, employers' reputation, faculty reputation and global view. In order to fulfil the demands of a changing world, the pursuit of quality and excellence in higher education ultimately calls for a strong focus on relevance, innovation, and partnership with industry.
4. Establishing research canter, selecting research chairs, and cultivating a learning environment where expectations are defined and the rewards of research are shared are all part of creating a culture of continuous progress inside the institution. Another crucial component of researcher development is collaboration, both domestically and internationally, since it offers chances for networking, resource sharing, and knowledge exchange. The advancement of academic and research activities is facilitated by scientific chairs and research canter, which supports innovation and growth that is driven by knowledge. All these important criteria are discussed based on the present scenario and global perspective. The university can improve research capacity and gain international recognition by placing a high priority on training and development.

P-1/2

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5. BSMRMU (Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Maritime University) road map highlights important strategies to become a top-tier institution of higher learning. The institution strives to attain academic excellence, advance knowledge based on research, and offer a superior learning environment. The first step on the road plan is accreditation, both domestically and internationally, to assure adherence to outlined quality standards. The institution's research culture can be improved by encouraging research and offering incentives like research prizes. In order to encourage innovation and have a bigger impact, collaborative initiatives should be prioritized both inside and outside of the university. The strategy also stresses the significance of ongoing education and training for researchers as well as the accessibility of research infrastructure. By carrying out these crucial tasks, BSMRMU hopes to grow its global networks and establish itself as a recognized institution. Overall, the report is very comprehensive for the development of a young university and the BSMRMU authority should implement the roadmap to improve research culture, support academic achievement, and have a positive social impact. It will foster innovation, advance society, and address social issues by encouraging research within the university, centres, laboratories and the departments.

As one of the stakeholders and as an academician in the field, I would like to request you to accept this research/report with recognition and proceed with further actions from your research centre as well as from the management of the university. I also want to thank your research centre for providing me the opportunity to review this report.

Yours sincerely,

(Prof. Dr. Mohammad Rafiqul Islam)
Vice Chancellor

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Abstract

Bangladesh's higher education system requires significant improvements to meet local and global demand. One of the significant challenges confronting Bangladesh's tertiary education system is "quality of teaching and research conditions." Improving quality was also identified as a key cross-cutting strategic goal of Bangladesh Higher Education reform frameworks. As a Higher education institution, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Maritime University, Bangladesh has taken a timely initiative to produce a roadmap. The research project highlights the strategies to become a top tier institution of higher study. It identifies the first step to the roadmap is the accreditation of the programs to ensure quality and worldwide acceptance. The second task is to create research culture through collaborative initiatives among academicians and students such as training and workshops. This Institutional Annual Research Initiative (IARI) will assist Higher Education Institutions such as BSMRMU and its academics in preparing and publishing world-class research papers in prestigious journals. Through research and scholarly activities, the institution will not only demonstrate its strong commitment to research activities. Still, it will also assist institutions in raising their profile and increasing their chances of being included in the QS University Ranking system.

Outlook of the report

The research project report on the Institutional Annual Research Initiative and QS University Ranking roadmap is divided into different chapters. The report starts with an introduction chapter which includes the background of the work, review of literature, overall objective and scope of works under the project. The following chapter is Accreditation, Rating and Ranking which discusses the Accreditation system, Rating system, Regional Ranking system and Global Ranking system. This chapter focuses on the suitable systems those are fitted for Bangladesh context.

The chapter-3 discusses the cases of the successful implementation of the roadmap of the world class university. The case study includes the initiatives taken by the countries such as China, Egypt, Thailand, Malaysia, and India.

The chapter-4 illustrates the importance of the Institutional Research Initiative, through Research Projects, Institutional Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC), Fortnightly Presentation, Research and Publications.

The chapter-5 covers various ways and means to Engaging Researchers Community. The is explained in terms of Annual International Seminar, Quarterly Seminar, On Campus Workshop, and On Campus Guest Lecture. These are the events that allows face to face meeting between the researchers, students and the industry.

The chapter-6 discusses about the requirements of the Training and Development of Researchers through National Collaboration, International Collaboration, establishment of Scientific Chair and Research Centre.

The chapter-7 provides a Roadmap for BSMRMU to achieve the mentioned goals in chapter 2-6. The roadmap is illustrated in steps, such as Phase-I Accreditation and Rating, followed by Reward. The Phase-II is Regional Ranking followed by Global Ranking. This chapter concludes with a proposal of an action plan to achieve these goals. Few important sections are includes at the end of the report such as acknowledgement and references.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Maritime University, Bangladesh (BSMRMU) is the first-ever maritime university of Bangladesh established by an act of the Parliament (act 47, 2013) on 26 October 2013. Soon after the inception, the university initiated its route towards maritime excellence. Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with reputed Maritime institutions around the world such as World Maritime University, Sweden, has been signed for necessary supports. This has allowed the BSMRMU to maintain high standards in education system. In 2014, Bangladesh has achieved the delimitation of maritime boundary with neighboring countries. This allowed Bangladesh to have complete control over the 118813 square kilometer of large sea area. Effective exploration and exploitation of the vast sea are therefore paramount towards the future of Bangladesh and its people. These will require the right kind of human resources and technological advancement at national level. BSMRMU with its motto 'We Strive for Maritime Excellence' is committed to provide necessary human resources and technological tools for the nation, through the creation of skilled and knowledgeable human resources. At present, BSMRMU is conducting only undergraduate and post-graduate (Masters) courses on various maritime related subjects in its temporary Dhaka campus. The process of the establishment of a permanent campus in Chittagong is ongoing. The permanent campus will allow other specialized fields of study to be opened. Thus, it will endeavor to emerge as a center of excellence in maritime higher education within the shortest possible time. Bangladesh's higher education system requires significant improvements to meet local and global

demand. One of the significant challenges confronting Bangladesh's tertiary education system is "quality of teaching and research conditions." Improving quality was also identified as a key cross-cutting strategic goal of Bangladesh Higher Education reform frameworks. It is a difficult task to publish papers in reputable scholarly journals in this day and age of open access publishing. Both academic and professional communities place a high value on the publication of scientific and technical papers. A member of the academic staff is usually expected by his or her institution to publish the results of his or her research work in a reputable journal. Authors frequently face a daunting task in improving their chances of publishing their research works in prestigious journals. Reputed journals reject many papers due to deficiencies in structure, methodological clarity, quality results, analysis, writing articulation, and so on. Most educational institutions do not provide formal training or specialized workshops on writing papers and publishing them internationally. As a result, Higher Education Institutions must develop a strategic vision for research and publication.

This Institutional Annual Research Initiative (IARI) will assist Higher Education Institutions such as BSMRMU and its academics in preparing and publishing world-class research papers in prestigious journals. Through research and scholarly activities, the institution will not only demonstrate its strong commitment to research activities. Still, it will also assist institutions in raising their profile and increasing their chances of being included in the QS University Ranking system.

This joint collaborative research will be conducted by BSMRMU and CBER, London, UK. While the annual research initiative recognizes the significance of the broader range of activities such as workshop and research works. The study also identifies the fundamental areas for improvement. These should be determined through extensive consultations and selected based on their uniqueness, their potential to draw on strengths from across the BSMRMU which is a combination of teaching, research, scholarly activities and creative works, public service activities, and their relevance to national and international priorities in today's rapidly transforming society. This annual

initiative must be considered an integral part of the University's Strategic Research Plan. This initiative will support the institution in taking specific research-related activities to foster research and collaboration.

Based on established strengths, signature areas connected to themes were selected and evaluated using criteria such as:

- Relevance to national and international issues of priority
- Impact on society
- Contributions to innovation and discovery
- Distinguished research leadership
- Significant cooperation and participation.

1.2 Institutional Quality

The public universities in Bangladesh are established by the act of law passed in the parliament. It is an integral part of the governance arrangements between its people and the country. The development of the country directly affects the universities in many ways. The Education Ministry does the relative works on behalf of the government. They act as a catalysis for the development of the education up to higher secondary level using various means by creating new schools and increasing competition among the private schools. The knowledge and skills such as language, communication, mathematics, and computing-based learning at the higher secondary level will help the student to develop the reasoning ability essentially required for the higher education. At the higher education level, the improvement of infrastructure, quality faculty members, improved quality student intake, and connection to society and its need for higher education. These are crucially entangled with each other. The results of the study can further be processed on the basis of the quality of institutions at global level.

1.3 University Ranking

The ranking of university provides the international recognition of its quality of education. It quantifies the various variables that ensure the quality of the education. There are a few widely accepted universities ranking system which includes the Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU), the Quacquarelli Symonds (QS) World University Ranking, and the Times Higher Education (THE) World University Ranking. The ARWU, was started as Shanghai Ranking, which is developed by the Centre for World-Class Universities at Shanghai Jiao Tong University. It is a non-profit work published by the Shanghai Jiao Tong University since 2009. A detail description of the ranking system is explained by Liu and Cheng (Liu and Cheng 2005)¹ and D. Docampo, D. Egret & L. Cram (Docampo, Egret, and Cram 2022)². The ARWU follows the following events as indices. The education standard, research profile of teachers, research output/publication, and academic performance. The ARWU also includes the number of Nobel prize winners in a particular institutions, any other prizes in the relevant field, most cited scientist, or papers published in Nature or Science are included in the ranking. In addition, universities with a significant number of papers indexed by the Science Citation Index-Expanded (SCIE) and Social Science Citation Index (SSCI) are also included³.

The Quacquarelli Symonds (QS) World University Ranking is designed to evaluate the quality of universities at global level. The evaluation is carried out on the following six performance indicators. These indicator provides an assessment on the universities from four perspectives, namely research, teaching, employability and internationalization. The big data is collected from public databases, global surveys of academics and graduate employers⁴. These performance indicators are academic reputation, employer reputation, student-to-faculty ratio, citations per faculty, international faculty ratio, and international student ratio. The academic reputation is evaluated using a global survey, in which people are asked questions about the institutions. These questions include inquiry about the best work information which

being conducted within their own field of research. In the same way to evaluate the employer reputation the system uses a global survey, which inquires about who produces the best graduates in the recent times.

The Times Higher Education World University Ranking uses several performance indicators that are divided into areas such as teaching, reputation, staff-to-student ratio, doctorate-to-bachelor's ratio, doctorates-awarded to-academic-staff ratio, income, reputation survey, research income, research productivity, citations, research influence, international outlook and industry income, knowledge transfer. The crucial indicators are the university's reputation for research and teaching among its peers are the responses to the annual Academic Reputation Survey⁵. The reputation data is provided with substantial weightage in the global rankings. This contains teaching quality and research quality. The teaching quality requires independent evaluation mostly by the accreditation or any appointed agencies. Many reputed international university conduct teachers evaluation which is done by the students. These evaluation are done anonymously through technology platforms for each of the semesters. The data is then analyzed and evaluated by independent professional agencies in the relevant fields. The evaluation is measured in a scale of 3-5.

The major data required for the global rankings of universities collected through online surveys. The process collects an average of one lakh expert opinions from various educational forums through surveys and questionnaires. In order to develop the universities to world class level, one can include professional agencies who can evaluate the performance of teachers and researchers. Citations per faculty are another key component that measures the research quality of an institution. The citations per faculty can be improved by producing research article coupled with publishing internationally recognize journals which are well indexed. The research output should also need to be linked with industry demands. It is obvious that a smaller number of students per faculty (30:1) enable students to have meaningful access to

teaching contents. The productivity of a teacher can be further improved through the 'Research Assistants' concept. It requires a separate fund for the students which are in practice in the international universities. This concept can be introduced in Bangladesh through the UGC. The candidate can be selected from students with graded score 3-4 to assist the teachers in research.

The foreign student and faculty ratio to the national is another major component that decides world rankings. In Bangladesh the enrollment of foreign students is in practiced but recruitment of foreign teachers is not allowed by the University grant commission (UGC). The UGC is an intermediate regulatory body that is tasked with the responsibility to distribute the government funds to the public universities. The major funds are sourced from the revenue budget. Thus it is limited for the citizens of Bangladesh only. The university can use a method to raise fund from the alumni and industry. This fund can be used for attracting international students and faculty members. These international faculty members and students who may also be part of professional ranking agencies may then enable the university to be recognized internationally and inculcate global awareness and outlook for the same.

1.4 Scope

The study is designed to assist institutions and their academic staff/management in understanding what they are doing well and how things can be improved concerning future research activities. A strong and continuous research programme can increase focus while allowing institutions to embed values essential to a healthy, dynamic culture in which everyone has a stake in the pursuit of excellence. IARI assists in the identification of crucial standards, criteria, tools, and outcomes required producing high-quality research output. Institutions discover that they can better appreciate their core beliefs and objectives. As a result, they have a clearer vision and understanding of what it takes to navigate the challenges that the constant pursuit of excellence brings.

In terms of scholarly activities, the Institutional annual research initiative (IARI) has the potential to be genuinely transformative for Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Maritime University. IARI should be well aligned with the institution's strategic research plan to be most effective.

The scope of the study is

- To identify the current research framework within the university (In the absence of a strategic research plan, the initiative will recommend that one be developed.)
- Examine the current provisions of research for the academic staff
- Special workshops and training on preparing and publishing research papers for the next academic cycle will be provided.
- Provide an awareness training workshop on the essential requirements for the QS world ranking and the institutional implications, and develop a roadmap as needed.

Thus it is possible to guide a university to become a world class university⁶. There are many examples where a 5-10 years plan was executed and the respective university has been included in the world class university list⁷. The concept is different in different region of the world. For Asia-Pacific region and to the third world, it is difficult to recognize the role of world class university in national growth⁸. The most challenging part is changing the culture towards research which again requires multilevel approach⁹.

1.5 Objectives

The main objective is to develop annual research-based activities to foster research and collaboration within the institution that will ensure robust research-led teaching philosophy. To achieve this the following objectives are set,

- To foster an institutional culture of research excellence that could aid the institution's eventual inclusion in world class university ranking and other university rating lists as a reputable institution.
- To develop and construct Institutional researchers for international renown and success.
- To enable academics and researchers to engage with the larger community and have a proven local, national, and global impact.
- To Create an elite research workforce and culture through continuous training and development

The study will set the path for the Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Maritime University in Dhaka, Bangladesh, to establish a comprehensive world-class research culture. The study will also support the delivery of specific training workshops on preparing and publishing research papers in reputable international scholarly journals, as well as raising awareness on becoming a reputable institution recognized by world university ranking system or other such recognition.

Chapter 2

Accreditation, Rating and Ranking

2.1 Introduction

This chapter explains the academic and educational performance of universities to the standard of internationally accepted world class universities through accreditation, rating and ranking. The process has come to light due to the global economic growth and development¹⁰. Such efforts will inevitably include the progressive development of successful strategies for academic and training excellence, funding, adequacy of support services, academic staff qualifications and postgraduate qualifications. Quality in higher education is not easy to define, but the significant increase in international competition and variability in the higher education sector, which has created a variety of courses, programs and degrees, has led to an increasingly necessary evaluation and assessment of quality insurance. In fact, quality assurance is a term that has many interpretations and includes the continuous evaluation, monitoring, protection, maintenance and improvement of the quality of higher education institutions. Practical improvement is the result of continuous quality assurance. Thus, it is inextricably linked to educational standards that measure outcomes that are used to benchmark against indicators. Quality assurance can be assessed through inspection and accreditation. High quality indicates high status and high reputation, a recognized measure of world-class excellence.

2.2 BAC Accreditation system

Bangladesh Accreditation Council (BAC) is established with the urge to promote and ensure quality assurance in university education in Bangladesh through implementing the national qualifications framework (NQF) and accredit the academic programs and higher education institutions. In the reality of global awakening in sustainable development, any country wishes to excel in knowledge and innovation must develop university education to world class level. The quality of higher education is based on comprehensive system of teaching, research and innovation. Thus, improving the quality of higher education is essential to participate in globalization and place the economy of Bangladesh on a skill based society¹¹. The BAC is established under the Bangladesh Accreditation Council Act, 2017 in March 2017. BAC will set the quality standards of higher education at the academic program and institution levels, and collaborate with both regional and international quality assurance (QA) agencies for international recognition of BAC and higher education of Bangladesh.

BAC is established to accredit academic programs and higher education institutions for quality assurance. In order to make its inception worth, the objective of BAC is set as follows¹²:

- “Serve as a national and internationally recognized quality assurance and accreditation agency;
- Facilitate the implementation of national qualifications framework and adoption of accreditation standards at the higher education institution (HEI) and academic program levels;
- Provide standards, guidelines and code of best practice to the higher education institutions (HEIs) for self-assessment and developing internal quality assurance culture;

- Provide consultation services, organize workshop, seminar and conference to create awareness and motivate the higher education community towards accreditation and capacity building to prepare for accreditation;
- Provide quality assurance and accreditation services to HEIs through mentoring and training for academics and professional staff as they implement accreditation standards and engage in continual quality improvement;
- Assure students and public about the quality of higher education, institutional integrity and accountability through rigorous implementation of accreditation standards, external quality assessment, academic audit and monitoring;
- Maintain liaison and develop cooperation with credible international and regional quality assurance networks and accreditation bodies in higher education; and
- Maintain a capable and sustainable organizational structure.”

2.2.1 The BAC accreditation Process.

a. Submitting the expression of interest

The first step of the accreditation is the IQAC of an institution will submit an expression of interest in writing to BAC. The accreditation manual other required services will be provided by the BAC. The concerned HEI/POE/IQAC will conduct self-assessment and assess the compliance in respect of BAC accreditation standards and criteria. The institution can appoint a mentor which will be used for consultation services. The mentor may conduct self-assessment of the program or the institution following the BAC accreditation manual and prepare the entity to apply for accreditation.

b. Self-Assessment

The institute that applied for accreditation, need to conduct self-assessment of concerned academic program following the guidelines mentioned in the chapter-4 of the BAC Manual within one year from the date of application. The self-assessment of

HEI/academic program is the beginning of the quality assurance and accreditation process. Self-assessment is useful to see the present status program level. Based on the present status of BAC accreditation standards the BAC will make decision regarding application for accreditation.

c. Eligibility to Apply for BAC Accreditation

The faculty/department/institute intent to apply for accreditation must fulfill the following conditions:

- 1) The academic program must be approved by the UGC or any appropriate authority in Bangladesh;
- 2) The institution must have a permanent IQAC for management of quality assurance.
- 3) As per the Bangladesh Accreditation Council Act, 2017 section 17(2) HEI/academic program must comply with the BNQF;
- 4) Only bachelor degree or above level of education program.
- 5) At least one batch of students must complete the graduation under the academic program at least two years before the date of application.
- 6) In case of institutional accreditation, at least 20% of total academic programs of the HEI must be accredited by BAC. Provided that the number of accredited academic program is minimum of three;
- 7) The academic institution should contain infrastructural facilities, separate human resources and funds to fulfill BAC standards and criteria;
- 8) The applying institute need to conduct self-assessment within one year from the date of application for accreditation. The self-assessment need to be conducted following the BAC accreditation manual.

d. Application for Accreditation

- 1) The applying entity need to submit the application form prescribed by the Council;

2) Complete document and other information must be submitted with the application following the directives of the Council;

e. Acceptance or Refusal of Application

1) An application filled properly and submitted with all necessary documents, it will be forwarded for further processing;

2) In case of rejection of the application, the Council may provide with seven days' notice period in writing for submission of required documents. After seven days, BAC shall reject the application and send back the application for resubmission.

3) Upon acceptance of the application, the council shall inform the applicant in writing to pay accreditation fee within next seven days.

f. Accreditation Fee

1) There is a fee to be paid in the favor of the BAC as specified in the Accreditation Rules, 2022.

g. Accreditation Standards and Criteria for Academic Program

The BAC Standards and criteria for program or institution accreditation are globally recognized and widely accepted in higher education. The program offering entity (POE) of Higher Education Institution (HEI) need to registrar appropriate documentations as evidence of compliance for each criterion 1-10 as mentioned in the accreditation policy¹³. The standards and criteria are generalized and applicable for all disciplines. There may be some criteria need to be discipline-specific for reasonable self-assessment. In the case of specific discipline an expert committee consisting reputed academics will be formed. The discipline-specific expert committee will provide discipline specific requirements relating to the identified criteria. The

Accreditation Committee for each HEI/POE will inquire and validate the availability, adequacy and appropriateness of these requirements for quality education.

2.3 IEB-BAETE Accreditation

The Institution of Engineers, Bangladesh (IEB) is widely recognized National Professional Organization for the accreditation of degrees or program in Bangladesh. IEB is registered under the Societies Registration Act of the government of Bangladesh. IEB works closely with all types of engineering fields. IEB- Board of Accreditation for Engineering and Technical Education (BAETE) became a provisional signatory to the Washington Accord in 2016¹⁴. BAETE Bangladesh, provides accreditation to the engineering programs which are offered by an institution mainly universities. BAETE only recognize the Institutions and programs which are approved by UGC or any government entity. The duration of the program is usually of four years where the admission requirements are higher secondary school certificates or equivalent. The program must contain a foundation in science and mathematics which leads to the professional practice of engineering. The accreditation of a program increases the social and academic value of the program. This also transforms a student into a capable engineer with knowledge of fundamentals and globally acceptable level of professional competence. The process of accreditation is also a way of promoting quality by introducing ethical competition among similar programs at various institutions nationally and internationally.

The accreditation of a program ensures that the graduates have the skills that are required for national and international competencies. In addition to that, it allows all of the stakeholders in locating engineering programs that meet national and international standards. The last but not the least, it provides a tool for the accumulation of existing engineering programs through evaluation and feedback.

Table-2.1 The steps for the accreditation application initiation process are as follows:

1	Submit application
2	Formation of the Evaluation Team
3	Communication to the institution about the formation of the Evaluation Team
4	Communication of the institution’s reservations about any member of the Evaluation Team, if any.
5	Review of the SAR
6	On-site visit
7	Evaluation Team report
8	Scrutiny by the Sectoral Committee
9	Response of the institution to factual matters
10	Recommendation of the Sectoral Committee
11	Decision of the Board
12	Communication of the decision to the institution

Table 2.2 The time line for the service is as follows:

Steps	Expected time
Formation of the Evaluation Team	03 weeks
Communication of the institution’s reservations	01 weeks
On-site visit	12 weeks
Report of the Evaluation Team	03 weeks
Scrutiny by the Sectoral Committee	02 weeks
Response of the institution to factual matters	01 weeks
Recommendation of the Sectoral Committee	02 weeks
Decision of the Board	16 weeks

2.4 Rating system

Quacquarelli Symonds (QS) Star is a university ranking system used by hundreds of institutions worldwide. Participating educational institutions take part in a comprehensive assessment in various areas such as teaching, facilities and innovation. At the beginning of the project, a dedicated QS Stars analyst is assigned to the project; the analyst will work with the university's primary contact to gather the necessary information and evidence. At the end of the evaluation, the educational institutions receive a general evaluation and a grade in at least eight categories. These grades are detailed in the QS Stars report, which is given to the university along with the graded certificate. If a university has a valid licence, it will also receive a set of QS Stars badges (available in JPG, PDF and PNG versions). These images show the scores obtained in each category and can be used in the university's own marketing materials. QS Star is a rating system that provides a detailed overview of an institution, enabling you to identify which universities are the best in the subjects you are interested in, such as program strength, opportunities, graduate employability, social responsibility, inclusion and more.

QS Stars understands that universities are different and therefore need to be rated in a number of categories that recognize different strengths. It also recognizes that every student is looking for something different and that not all universities - even the highest quality institutions - are right for every student. Using QS Stars when searching for a prospective program helps you understand which universities performed well against a comprehensive list of indicators, enabling you to match your interests with universities that are strong in the subjects that matter to you. The QS Stars method rates universities using dozens of indicators in at least eight categories. After the evaluation, the universities are awarded with a composite star score, which varies from 0 to 5 stars, depending on the score obtained as a result of the evaluation.

2.4.1 Core criteria

The core criteria to become a world class university are a matter of discussion and argument around the world. The matter has become more interesting with the growing popularity of university ranking and rating. The surveys around the academia and industry show volunteer involvement regarding the data collection. There are several methods and institutions that publish world ranked university data. The core criteria used in the rankings and other assessments is generalized for all of the university though it is different which is a challenge to evaluate all of the institution at the same scale¹⁵. QS Stars rating system rates a program or universities rather than rank them. The method for rating QS Stars is based on quality assessment.

a. Research

Research is the basic element that differentiates between a local and a world class university. In this category, quality of research, productivity in terms of article published and student guided for masters and PhD, number of citation per article and international awards.

b. Academic Development

The Academic Development means the procedure that a university follows to develop its learning environment. It also focuses on the institution's efforts to enhance the student learning experience outside of the classroom. It can be assessed in terms of field trip, internship. In this category the availability of academic learning centers for students as well as teaching and research assistant opportunities are considered.

c. Teaching

The role of a university is to foster the finest minds, which in turns inspires the next generation. This will produce future research scholars. But to do that one must be a teacher first. Hence teaching is considered as the most challenging task in this changing world. To ensure the best teaching quality, an assessment must be continued. This can

be done by gathering student's feedback through anonymous student surveys and student faculty ratio.

d. Employability

In the twenty first century, with the ever changing trends and competition, the graduate employability is considered more than academic strength. This is in conscious with the community, which focuses on the ability to contribute effectively in a multicultural team. This includes the skills set to deliver presentations, managing people, taking assignment; completing projects moreover become a competitive resource. The basic indicators data is collected through surveys of employers. The university can provide graduate employment rates and careers service support through various community such as alumni, forum and carrier club.

e. Internationalization

The rating of program considers the proportion of international students and staff to the locals. This can be ensured through the international relation cell which records the numbers of exchange students and visiting professors from various nationalities. This also includes the strength of international collaboration with other universities. The collaboration can be in the form of joint research program, student exchange and visiting faculty members.

2.4.2 Advanced Criteria

The Advanced Criteria sorts out the university with a firm foundation in ensuring the core criteria. If an institute ensures the core criteria, they may advance to a higher level of performance. Since institutions vary in specialization, this allows them to select two of the four categories explained below.

a. Social Responsibility

Engagement measures how truly a university takes its responsibilities to society by devoting in the local community. This includes charity work, awareness works and disaster relief. The social responsibility can be extended to regional human capital development and environmental awareness.

b. Innovation

Innovation measures the output of a university's activities and findings to the country in terms of economy, society and culture. This has become increasingly relevant for universities. Though innovation is now considered as an integral part of incubation center.

c. Arts & Culture

This is an inclusion in the indicator system due to encourage the cultural exchange between national and international students. It is measure in the number of festivals and exhibitions organized by the institution.

d. Inclusiveness

This is a particular part of the rating system which focuses on the accessibility of the students to scholarships, grants, disability access, gender balance and low-income outreach. This ensures the equal participation of the students from the various parts of the societies such as village, hill tracts, ethnic, low income commodities etc.

e. Learning Environment

The Learning Environment means the campus. It looks at the experience of the staff and students within the university environment. The data can be extracted by online survey for the commodities. The assessment is performed both on the physical and online learning environment.

f. Facilities

The infrastructure ensures proper offerings to the staff and its students. This includes the facilities and services that a university can provide. Thus infrastructure is an indicator that enhances the experience of a student towards the university. This is in particular sporting, internet, library, security and medical facilities.

g. Online Learning

This grouping looks at various indicators such as student services and technology, track record, student faculty commitment, student collaboration, commitment to online and standing of the university.

2.4.3 Subject Rating

There are 31000 universities which are ranked by the webometrics each year¹⁶. It is published by the Cybermetrics Lab, Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Madrid, Spain. To narrow the search for world class universities, subject can also be ranked. There are many universities which emphasizes on a single subject rather than the university as a whole. This is often the case for new universities and subject which are established due to the demand from the stakeholders and alumni. Besides there are specialist institution those focus on a general subject area or narrow area of expertise. In the competitive world, to advance in the world university ranking, universities have specialized subject areas in which they can outshine beyond all others.

The QS Stars rating system provides a comprehensive audit of the performance of a program and rates it with stars. The criteria are same as explained in section 2.4.2 for institution.

OVERALL		1000
Institutions must have at least:		
5+	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 Star ratings in all categories and meet all prerequisites needed for 5 Stars 	900
5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5% international faculty 5% international students 70 points in the Learning Environment category 85 points in the Employability category 150 academic referees OR 3 citations per faculty member* 105 points in the Teaching category^ 	700
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1% (OR 25% of the regional average) international students 75 academic referees OR at least 2 citations per faculty member* 85 points in the Teaching category^ 	550
3		400
2		250
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Must have the authority to grant valid degree-level programs in its own name 	100

* If assessed in Research category
^ If assessed in Academic Development category

Figure 2.1 QS star rating chart-1

Figure 2.2 QS star rating chart-2

Figure 2.3 QS star rating process flow chart

2.5 Global Ranking Systems

The global university ranking system is introduced in the 2004 onward by various institutes and companies. This has become popular in the recent time with the globalization of education and information through World Wide Web. The ranking of universities is mainly to attract the best students and faculty members. There are mainly three ranking system which are mostly used globally. With different methodologies, Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU), which is conducted by Shanghai Jiao Tong University¹⁷, the Times Higher Education (THE) World University Rankings¹⁸, and the Quacquarelli Symonds (QS) World University Rankings¹⁹ are the three ranking system which are used globally. In the list of world university ranking, the first thousand universities are considered to be the most attractive. Thus the ranking system filters the universities which draw the attention of the students, faculty

members, stakeholders and global communities. These universities are thought to be the supplier of the global knowledge market. Of course, all of the ranking focuses in research rather than teaching this is due to the fact that, the research output can be assessed through publication, patents, conferences, incubation, products innovation etc. On the other hand, teaching is a continuous process of learning and knowledge transfer, which is being evaluated through exam. This will provide the number of graduates produced in a given time.

The world university ranking of program and universities shows the standardization of education of a country. The university education is a terminal level education which allows a student to enter into the work force of a country. The ranking gives an idea of the quality of an educational institute which helps the commodity like students and parents to choose the best institute for their future. The terminal level of education like secondary, higher secondary and bachelor degree; each of these certificates allows a students to participate in the recognized business/job/entrepreneurship market. Thus the standard of the education provided by these institutions directly represents the performance of a sector in the country's economic growth. This also related to the intellectual development of a country through the quality of public services. Many developing countries in south Asia and beyond, are suffering from the sustainable development. The visible development can be an addition in quantity. But the service is measured in quality where we lack behind. The quality of education can provide sustainable growth on an economy. The quality of education is ensured by accreditation from recognize body such as Bangladesh accreditation council. The quality of education through accreditation has become a common practice among the world best ranked universities. Universities in the list of first thousand become a model and education hub for a region. This attracts students from neighboring regions and other countries. The impact of a world class university in the national and regional development is now a proven fact. A ranked university not only produces skill human resource but also encourage other institution to come to the standard. To focus on the

element of the university to bring the institution to world class standard we need to see Table 2.3 for global university ranking criteria set by different organizations. To begin with as a novice institution, one can start with developing a teaching standard which starts with competence faculty members. This will also increase the academic reputation. In parallel to this, an institution needs to fund research so the faculty members can produce significant number of research article. This will enhance the research, citation, international outlook, citation per faculty etc.

Organisations	Criteria	Percentage
Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU)	Alumni	10%
	Awards	20%
	Highly cited researchers	20%
	Papers in Nature and Science	20%
	Papers indexed	20%
	Per capita performance	10%
	Total	100%
QS World University Rankings	Academic reputation	40%
	Employer reputation	10%
	Faculty/Student Ratio	20%
	Citations per faculty	20%
	International Faculty Ratio	5%
	International Student Ratio	5%
Total	100%	
Times Higher Education (THE)	Teaching (the learning environment)	30%
	Research (volume, income and reputation)	30%
	Citations (research influence)	30%
	International outlook (staff, students, research)	7.5%
	Industry income (knowledge transfer)	2.5%
Total	100%	

Table 2.3 Global University ranking criteria in percentages²⁰.

The ranking of universities are now well accepted in the students, parents and stakeholders community. In the recent days, QS World University Rankings and Times Higher Education World University Rankings are most widely accepted in the academic domain. However, the entire ranking data base uses its own set criteria and weightages which are shown in the table 2.1²¹. On the other hand, though QS World University Rankings emphasizes academic reputations, which is 40% of total weights, the research

weight is not negligible at all. Besides all of these three ranking system, there is another system called, The Webometrics Ranking (2004). The Webometrics ranking system extracts the metadata from the website of the university. The extraction of metadata is also acquired from the various web platforms where university activities are presents²². Thus, the platforms of ranking universities emphasize mainly on the teaching, alumni satisfaction, research output and industry affiliation of universities²³.

In the context of Bangladesh, it was thought that the idea of having a world class university is a luxury. But Bangladesh is in the path of becoming a middle income country in the next five years. With the economic growth rate, it is a matter of time when we will require national level innovation and indigenously developed technology. We will be requiring our own patents for a product such as medicine, automobile, food etc. At present we are hiring a large number of foreign experts and engineers for any development projects. Thus the cost of have a service in Bangladesh is always highest. Thus we must focus on making at least one or two world class university in Bangladesh to keep us in the path for a prosperous and self-dependent country.

Chapter 3

Case study

3.1 Introduction

At the age of 18-20, a student need to take one the most critical decisions; which university to be admitted or which subject to study? This particular path affects the future of an individual. It similarly affects the student in his/her social and economic status of the life. To ease the process of choosing a university, the ranking of universities has become a solution. In the recent years (2010-2022) a numbers of global ranking systems is being setup by different organizations. The global ranking system helps the students and their parents to take the best decision for their future. At the beginning these ranking are limited to developed countries but now a days many university from around the world came to the best university list. More or less most of the countries now have at least one university which is in the best one thousand university list. The global university ranking provides statistical data of the university which allows the student to study the information. The information includes, the teacher student ratio, foreign students to national student ratio, reputation, campus life etc. In this chapter, few success stories of universities are discussed which have excelled in reaching the world university ranking. Each of these universities are discussed regarding their struggle for the inclusion in the global university ranking

3.2 Bangladesh

In Bangladesh there are 53 public and 103 private universities which give a total of 154 universities²⁴. Among these, 60-70 universities are ranked by at least one of the world university ranking system²⁵. These ranking systems include a) Webometrics Ranking Web of Universities, b) Scimago Institutions Rankings, c) QS University Rankings, d) THE World University Rankings. Considering the Webometrics Ranking Web of Universities, the name of BSMRMU could be found ranked 84 among Bangladesh and 12882 among the world²⁶. A part of the data base is provided in the Table-3.1.

Table 3.1 List of universities of Bangladesh ranked by the Webometrics Ranking Web of Universities in January 2023.

Bangladesh

ranking	World Rank	University
1	987	University of Dhaka
2	1225	Rajshahi University
3	1382	Shahjalal University of Science & Technology
4	1449	Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology
5	1844	North South University Bangladesh
6	2077	Jahangirnagar University
7	2146	Brac University
8	2326	Bangladesh Agricultural University
9	2422	Daffodil International University
10	2433	University of Chittagong
11	2473	Noakhali University of Science & Technology
12	2780	Khulna University
13	2842	Khulna University of Engineering & Technology
14	2982	Independent University Bangladesh
15	3080	Rajshahi University of Engineering and Technology
16	3215	East West University Bangladesh
17	3232	Chittagong University of Engineering and Technology
18	3357	(4) Ahsanullah University of Science & Technology
19	3371	Jagannath University
20	3405	Mawlana Bhasani Science & Technology University
21	3427	American International University Bangladesh
22	3457	Jessore University of Science & Technology
23	3541	International Islamic University Chittagong
24	3644	Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Agricultural University
25	3779	Dhaka University of Engineering & Technology
26	3848	University of Asia Pacific Bangladesh
27	3909	Sher-e-Bangla Agricultural University
28	3966	Southeast University
29	3993	Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science & Technology University Dinajpur
30	3998	Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University
31	4049	United International University
32	4060	Sylhet Agricultural University (Sher-e-Bangla Agricultural University)
33	4073	Military Institute of Science & Technology
34	4129	Islamic University Kushtia
35	4132	Begum Rokeya University Rangpur
36	4425	University of Liberal Arts Bangladesh
37	4494	International University of Business Agriculture and Technology University of Dhaka
38	4557	Green University of Bangladesh
39	4678	Islamic University of Technology
40	4714	Patuakhali Science & Technology University
41	4830	Comilla University

42	5001	Chittagong Veterinary and Animal Sciences University.	66	9153	Atish Dipankar University of Science & Technology.
43	5380	Stamford University Bangladesh	67	9377	Bangladesh University of Business and Technology.
44	5491	National University Bangladesh	68	9382	Chittagong Medical College
45	5689	University of Science & Technology, Chittagong	69	9410	Pabna University of Science & Technology.
46	5717	Asian University for Women	70	9470	Rajshahi Medical University.
47	5740	World University of Bangladesh	71	9626	BGMEA University of Fashion & Technology.
48	5748	Northern University Bangladesh	72	9663	City University Bangladesh
49	5775	Dhaka International University.	73	9714	Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Science and Technology University.
50	6102	(1) BGC Trust University, Bangladesh	74	9834	Premier University Chittagong
51	6141	Uttara University.	75	9884	Armed Forces Medical College Dhaka
52	6144	(1) Dhaka Medical College	76	10068	Asian University of Bangladesh
53	6214	Southern University Bangladesh	77	10427	East Delta University.
54	6360	State University of Bangladesh	78	10427	Sir Salimullah Medical College
55	6511	Gono University.	79	11918	First Capital University of Bangladesh
56	6693	Primeasia University.	80	12162	Mymensingh Medical College
57	7354	Bangladesh University of Professionals	81	12573	Presidency University Bangla Desh
58	7604	Bangladesh Open University.	82	12711	Jatiya Kabi Kazi Nazrul Islam University.
59	7781	Manarat International University.	83	12741	Bangladesh Medical College
60	7911	Eastern University Bangla Desh	84	12882	Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Maritime University.
61	8318	Leading University.	85	12882	Sheikh Fazilatunnesa Mujib
62	8560	Barisal University.			
63	8703	University of Information Technology & Sciences			
64	8905	University of Development Alternative			
65	9076	Metropolitan University Sylhet			

86	12925	Varendra University	98	16249	Rangpur Medical College
87	13050	(3) University of Dhaka Institute of Statistical Research and Training	99	16565	Habiganj Agricultural University
88	13484	Prime University			Bangladesh Army International
89	13597	European University of Bangladesh	100	16618	University of Science & Technology, Comilla
90	13597	SZMC Shaheed Ziaur Rahman Medical College			
91	14042	Bangladesh University of Textiles			
92	14479	Khulna Agricultural University			
93	14566	Sylhet International University			
94	14596	Islamic Arabic University			
95	14828	ASA University Bangladesh			
96	15561	Bangladesh University			
97	15869	Rajshahi Medical College			

3.3 China

China has become the global leader in developing the local universities in to a global university. China alone produces 20 % of all the academic publications globally²⁷. The growth rate of the scientific publication in China in the past ten years is around 8% per annum²⁸. The United States National Science Foundation (NSF) reported that the article published in 2008 was 1,755,850 globally which has increased to 2,555,959 in the year 2018²⁹. Globally, the Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) publication has shown a growth of 0.71% over the period of 2008-2018. In the United States, the publication number only in the year of 2018 is 4,22,808, Germany 1,04,396, Japan 98,793, UK 97,681, Russia 81,579, Italy 71,240, South Korea 66,376 and France 66,352. The data has shown the significance of the publication in the growth and development of the country.

Figure 3.1 The number of publication by the top eight countries in the year 2018.

In the figure 3.1, it is surprise to see the China in the top of the list which is also seen in the country’s economic rise. China realized the importance of the academic progress in the late nineties. As a consequence to that China has initiated the process to create world-class research university³⁰. Today we see the rise of China as a regional leader in the Indo-Asia-pacific policies and strategies. This was possible only due to the top-down policy in generating the required momentum for creating world Class University³¹.

3.4 Egypt

In the recent years (2010-2020), many countries in the world is working on the creation of a world class university to produce skilled human resource and hub of innovation through higher education. A generation in the twenty first century world requires competing capacity in the global marketplace. This can only be achieved by indigenous

development of technology and ideas. As a middle-east country, with vast resource, Egypt initiated to build World Class University under higher education reform plan in 2003 which was initiated for the government universities³². The features that a world class university should have and the requirements to have a world class university or to transform a local university into one are two different challenges. To understand the problem at a national level few questions need to be answered. It starts with what does it mean?, what are the essential features and characteristics?, How will it affect the present system? Once these are answered by the leadership, then the second phase of questions are raised. What are the bottlenecks in the higher education system?, what initiatives can be taken in Egypt? And finally, what strategic approach needs to be used for Egypt to develop its world-class universities? The critical analysis of the answers to these questions shows surprising results. It shows that there are many common pitfalls encountered that aim at establishing a new flagship institution over short period of time. At present Egypt have 14 universities those are ranked in QS world university ranking 2023 in between 416-1400³³.

3.5 Thailand

Many universities in Thailand adapted the National Education Act 2002 for the development of the institutions. The guideline was implemented in the 12th “National Social and Economic Development Plan – 2017-2021”. This plan has acted as the drive towards having a world class university in Thailand. At present, there are 10 universities of Thailand those are ranked in between 224-1400 in QS world University ranking 2023. Thailand followed a model which contained five fundamental guidelines which gave it the globally ranked ten universities^{34, 35}. The guideline includes the factors mainly a) administrative formation, b) strategy to place leadership personnel in the executive body, and c) strategy to place leading academicians. A dream cannot be come to reality without resources. This is a particular place where the development cannot be seen over

the year. It requires visionary works and patience. Besides the monetary resources, success in the focused innovation for a particular field is crucial. The success from a university comes through the students and teachers. The development of student potential in research, social, communication, knowledge will provide the institution with high quality human resource. All of the above three element will not work if the overall efficiency of the university does not improve. One part cannot operate without the others. Thus institute must be flexible in making stream line operation. Moreover, the institute as a whole must contain an international mindset to overcome any obstacle.

All of the above discussed five points for the success of the Thai institutions are state by K. Chaeddhananan, and N. S Dhirathiti, 2022 which are quoted¹¹ and illustrated in figure 3.2 “The process of the administrative drive consists of five steps as follows.

1. The University administrator recruitment, succession strategy, and action plans. This is an acquisition of qualified executives for administrative positions in order to formulate policies, plans, and annual objectives.
2. Resource allocation. This is the allocation and management of monetary and non-monetary resources in order to motivate, reduce change-inducing resistance, and develop the potential of human resources.
3. Work system determination. This is the collaboration among agencies and related component groups by formulating operation steps and solving problems to enhance performance efficiency in order to achieve the goals.
4. Organizational structure design. This is the design to change, improve and merge work structures in accordance with strategies of the organization, and when compared with competitors, by taking into consideration criteria relating to performance outcomes.
5. Organizational culture development. This is a process of change and development of organizational culture in order for personnel to have values and behaviors that support operations to achieve strategic goals of an organization”.

Thus, strategic management is viewed as a crucial tool for current organization management with an ever changing environment and continuous impacts on organizational operations.

Figure 3.1 The applied model proposed K. Chaedhananan, and N. S Dhirathiti, 2022 for the higher education in Thailand ¹¹.

3.6 Malaysia

The major changes in the Asian regions are initiated by the higher education policy of Malaysia. It has been possible by changing the relation between the state, university and market. The government of Malaysia made it their national interest. The dominance of the state in the university autonomy is always there since 1960. In year 2007, Malaysia formulated “National Higher Education Action Plan, 2007–2010” followed by the “National Higher Education Strategic Plan 2020”. These two plans provided the higher education institutions with greater autonomy. This enhanced autonomy worked and today Malaysia have developed number of world class universities which are globally acknowledged. Though the greater autonomy does not resolve many issues in “University and University Colleges Act, 1995” for public universities³⁶. Till the date, the public universities are totally dependent on the State for resources, and this need to be resolved. At present there are 24 universities those are ranked between 70-1200 in QS world university ranking 2023³⁷.

3.7 India

India as a developing county in the south Asia has contributed equally in the field of science, space, technology and engineering. It has the massive number of higher educational schools with 1043 universities, 42343 colleges and 11779 stand-alone institutions. It has placed it in the list of prestige and elite institutes. The “National Education Policy-2020” will provide the necessary momentum removing the bottlenecks and limitations. The policy has outlined few of these limitations such as rigid separation among the disciplines, access in critical locations, inadequate number of skilled teachers, and absence of competitive educational and research. According to the University Grants Commission of India, the total number of universities in India was 874 in 2018. That figure includes 47 central universities, 391 state universities, 125 deemed universities, and 311 private universities. The research output from these institutions was 48,998 science and engineering articles in 2008. This increased to 1,35,788 articles in 2018 at an average annual growth rate of 10.73% and the country now accounts for

5.31% of the total world publications in science and engineering. With over 1.35 lakh scientific papers published, India has become the world's third-largest publisher of science and engineering articles, according to US government agency data. The 2023 QS World University Rankings (WUR) shows that, India is holding 41 institutes in the ranking between 155-1400.

3.8 Strategy

The strategy to achieve quality and excellence in higher education can be called in many ways. We must build our academic reputation by establishing our mission and ensuring that our research is meaningful or relevant to society. In terms of employer reputation, it shows how institutions prepare their students for successful careers and which institutions produce the most qualified, innovative and advanced graduates. In this regard, we have to achieve extensive communication with students in recent months. From these discussions emerged a number of ways to strengthen students' careers and skills, culture and value systems. Student learning can be enhanced by introducing rural immersion programs, design thinking and entrepreneurship courses, Tinkerers Labs and Maker Spaces programs to create well-rounded students. One of the main strengths of the mass population is its endless desire to seek information. Asia is home to the world's oldest universities, which in ancient times were the center of higher education and cultural exchange. That is why our educational institutions have a rich heritage of research and learning. With modern learning, we have adapted well to the changing environment - focusing more on research and development, entrepreneurship and innovation. In addition to mathematical and analytical discipline, our universities focus on adapting their education to the needs of society. Overall, our education system prepares our graduates with technological and related skills that enable them to be at the helm of affairs in large global companies.

Ms. Falguni Suthar and Dr. Bhavesh Patel from Acharya Motibhai Patel Institute of Computer Studies, Ganpat University, India, have outlined the strategy for Achieving Quality and Excellence in Higher Education which are given as follows 3.8.1-3.8.22³⁸.

3.8.1 “With the developing Learning Society, increasing information technologies and education have grown many times. This growing education must be transformed into a learning society by higher education institutions, because in the future all human activities will require the contributions of experts.

3.8.2 Higher education institutions should not only invest more in physical infrastructure, but also place much more emphasis on teaching, learning and research programs. They have to transform the educated society into a learning society to meet the unpredictable future.

3.8.3 The output of the educational institution is the input for the industry. Institutions must strategize their industry engagement through their active representation. The job of educational institutions is not only to produce diplomas, but also to produce graduates with skills that will enable them to adapt to a competitive and hostile global environment.

3.8.4 Institutes have to develop curricula in consultation. The industry should be engaged and encouraged to place students as interns on their projects.

3.8.5 Teachers should be encouraged to use case studies and industry reports in teaching.

To improve quality and competitiveness, institutions need to standardize the curriculum and align it with industry requirements. A well-designed curriculum is strategic and reciprocal.

3.8.6 It requires a set of goals, objectives, with a systematic sequence of topics and study material that must be mutually accepted, accepted and formally approved by the institution and industry. It should include knowledge, learning attitudes, ability and general cognitive ability that enable students to develop awareness.

3.8.7 The survival of educational institutions depends on the success of the student. The mutually developed curriculum should be industry-focused rather than

test- and examination-driven. The industry continues its existence with the skilled, efficient and effective human resources it receives from educational institutes.

3.8.8 The objective of the institution will be achieved if its contributions are prepared with quality and excellence and are transformed from raw to efficient and effective results through a rigorous academic process and absorbed with appreciation. Such an outcome will establish institutional respect and goodwill in society.

3.8.9 Higher education institutions are known for their quality teaching, which is possible if they have research-oriented teachers and complementary salary and incentive policies. Research orientation develops the attitude of teachers to find solutions to relevant problems, and this attitude is the main strength of an excellent academic institution.

3.8.10 Innovative and career-oriented courses with the necessary skills for the survival, growth and development industry and students await. Such specialized and innovatively designed courses make students competitive and employable. These new courses can only be successful if institutions motivate teachers and motivation comes only through compensation and recognition.

3.8.11 Survival in the age of competition is only possible if educational institutions are highly innovative in reframing, redesigning and reinventing themselves. Being innovative means more than just adopting competitive technologies or implementing a new approach. Innovation leads to structure and practices that promote healthy and effective changes.

3.8.12 Most teachers in higher education work without any training in teaching, learning and assessment techniques. Institutions have to provide research-based education to make teachers more efficient in teaching. Recognized and highly respected retired teachers and industry professionals should share their teaching and research experience with untrained teachers.

3.8.13 To short-term excellence, institutions must provide improvement and periodically assess their strengths and weaknesses. They must demonstrate a high degree of determination to set standards and achieve success. Institutions must

keep their standards high if they want to be a leader in their field. Academic performances of students and teacher indicate the status of the institute.

3.8.14 The use of higher education is to develop strength, expertise and skills to solve life problem. Institutions should explore the potential of students and emphasize the importance of business and entrepreneurship. In particular, students in the commercial, managerial and technical fields must explore their employable skills.

3.8.15 Thanks to technology, education has penetrated to the farthest corners and leveled the field of opportunity for all. Higher education institutions should continue to increase their strength by adopting new competitive technologies related to the education sector. Institutes of improved technology can shape the vision of academic achievement for all participants.

3.8.16 Thanks to technology, institutions can develop global awareness; creativity, collaborative problem-solving and self-learning instinct among students and other academic participants. Higher education institutions will be able to keep up with the pace of competition only by adopting the dominant technologies of the era.

3.8.17 Higher education institutions need a global perspective in their mission and vision if they are to compete in the knowledge economy. They need to use research, innovation, personality and human resource development as well as education to transfer knowledge from one generation to the next through interaction with students and staff from around the world.

3.8.18 Education is absolutely necessary for social development, peace and justice. To be an excellent institution, they must demonstrate a high degree of commitment to social and cultural inclusion. Institutions are required to conduct student satisfaction and exit surveys after completing their studies. The results of such surveys should be taken into account in planning and policy making.

3.8.19 A good academic institution is always engaged in research activities. Quality and excellence of educational institutions is judged through research participation. Teachers develop necessary knowledge and skills and become effective academic

leaders. Institutes should encourage research, recognize teacher's efforts in research work and also encourage students to adopt research projects.

3.8.20 Extracurricular activities discover students' potential and lead to their total development. Participation in such activities is directly related to their development of self-esteem, self-improvement and leadership qualities. It also contributes to better grades, higher academic goals, and self-control by reducing delinquency.

3.8.21 Present education system should enhance the aptitude / potentiality of the students. Much more focus on the score oriented mindset affects the ability of the students. Monotonous type of teaching creates disinterest of the students towards particular subjects.

3.8.22 The system of education should be learning-centric rather than exam-centric. Extra-curricular activities should be arranged for the development of the student. We should include project-based learning, an interactive method in which children can explore the problems and challenges of the real world”.

Chapter 4

Institutional Research Initiative

4.1 Introduction

Institutional research has become a signature component in developing a society. It strengthens the society and a country by the inclusion of new idea, innovation and solution to problems. Institutions like institutes, universities, centers, labs, departments are the hub of regional exchange of culture and knowledge. These are also the hub of the communal and historical meeting points. Hence the institutional research initiative supports, protects, and respects the research activities for all they do for their communities and states³⁹. The Institutional Research Initiative (IRI) works through researchers, and industry collaboration. Various scholarships and internships provide the driving forces which are termed as IRI. This particular goal can be achieved in various ways which are discussed in this chapter such as research projects for students and teachers, Institutional quality assurance (IQAC), public presentation, research and publications.

4.2 Research Projects

The research projects are an institutional procedure to distribute funds among the students and teachers. The task plays a vital role in aligning the mission and vision of the institution through research output⁴⁰. Thus the research projects are carefully chosen by the committee as such it addresses the needs of the community. In the case of “Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman Maritime University (BSMRMU), Bangladesh, Post Graduate Research Management and Technology Transfer Centre (PRMTTC)” is responsible for organizing, managing and conducting the research for BSc honor’s projects, Master’s thesis, M.Phil. and Ph.D. research programs. The center is open for all the department and institutes of BSMRMU. PRMTTC is responsible for the

organization of various activities such as guest and internal faculty member lectures. These lectures are chosen on the research topic provided by the individual. The presentation mimics the current research conducted by the respective faculty member. The center also arranges research workshop for various skill development such as writing scientific articles. PRMTTC is tasked with the allocation of the annual research fund. Utilizing the fund PRMTTC funds various students project and thesis work through the faculty members. The center have produced number of publications in the reputed journal and conferences as the outcome of the research it has funded over the last six years⁴¹.

The fund is an essential part of the research force. At BSMRMU, the research fund is received from Government of Bangladesh through Ministry of Education and from the external source. In general, there are two kinds of research fund. One is 'UGC research fund for teacher' and another is 'BSMRMU research fund'. In a year these two funds are in total of around 10 million BDT. Apart from these government funds, there are other funds called Netherlands Universities Foundation for International Cooperation 'NUFFIC' which is the Dutch organization for internationalization in education. It is obtained from The Netherlands as grant. This grant is also used in various sector of Institutional development.

4.3 IQAC

A world class university is defined by its quality. It withholds the standard through quality of its operation, teaching and research. Understanding the quality is a different matter. It has various standards depending on the regions and resources. To ensure quality, in 2014, the UGC, Bangladesh instructed every university to have an Institutional Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC)⁴². The IQAC shall be responsible for the communication to the agencies which are reputed for the acknowledgement of the standard of an institution. To do so, "Government of Bangladesh (GoB) and the World

Bank”⁴³ has funded a project known as “Higher Education Quality Enhancement Project (HEQEP)”. This project allowed all of the universities to have an IQAC^{44, 45}. The IQAC will conduct internal evaluation of the standard of service, teaching and research. They are responsible to keep records which will be submitted to the standardization agencies. IQAC also arranges periodical workshop, training and exposure visit to maintain a global standard in the particular institution. The feedback mechanism is the most important job that is done by IQAC. It takes data from the staff, students and faculties. The data is processed and published annually as a report which shows the standard of the institution. The function of IQAC is such that it is the gateway to the recognition as the world class university.

4.4 Fortnightly Presentation

An academic discussion between faculty members enhances the teaching capacity of individual. This can be achieved in various manner such as public talks and lecture series. To be in an official manner, this can be achieved by a weekly or fortnightly seminar or lecture⁴⁶. This seminar can be arranged by the departments to enhance the teaching and presentation capacity of individuals. In case of a larger scale any faculty can arrange the presentation for all the department under that faculty. The presentation is emphasized on the research conducted of the individual faculty members. This also allows the faculty members to explore new ideas and produce work which will be useful for students to conduct research project and thesis. At BSMRMU, this is being practiced from 2017. This presentation is conducted in terms of phases. At presents it is in 6th phase. In each phase, every faculty member presents his/her own research. Once all of the faculty members have complete the presentation, the phase is completed. The next phase is again designed with a new schedule by putting all of the faculty members. This is repeated each year. The yearly average of the number of presentation is 24. The weekly or fortnightly seminar is presented in the presence of the Vice Chancellor, academic advisor, deans and head of the departments. All of the

faculty member participates in the seminar. This is a practice which is widely accepted in the academia in the sense of the increasing the enthusiasm among the young teachers.

4.5 Research

The twenty first century has shown the growth of the development of technology which the human kind have never seen in the past. History has shown many civilized and developed society had fallen only due to lack of innovation at some point when the rise was at its peak. Learning from the past, now a days it became a thumb rule through publish or perish. It is believed that without the innovation, the development can only sustain for a decade or so. Innovation makes a development sustainable. The universities are said to be the origin of innovation for a particular society. There are few elements that makes a university center of innovation which includes teaching, culture, lab, campus facility, library, industry hub etc.⁴⁷. Though teaching and certification was thought to be the basic task of an educational institute, this concept has changed. Now a days a world class university must contain three signature element. First, research output in terms of publication and patents. Second, reputation in the society and third, strong industry academia relation for funds. To maintain a steady research output, it is crucial of universities to participate in fundamental and applied research. For some world class universities the research is extended to technology, engineering and computational mathematics, machine learning etc.⁴⁸. Besides the innovation and industry relation, the environment of creative thinking and work place must be installed. This is a part of providing world class facility for having a world class university. The most expensive part of a world class university is its research funding which is in many case expensive. Even the mathematical computation and simulation requires super computer⁴⁹. Even with all of the above facilities, it comes to the capacity and capability of the faculty members and the students. The faculty

members must write research proposal to funding agencies and include students and staff. In many cases, the university need to invest in developing basic laboratory facilities which is also expensive for engineering and biological research. In the case of medical research it requires higher standard as it involves human and animal as subject. It is mainly done through the university medical center which has the authority to recruit doctors, intern medical students and industry as a member to the research community. Research business, arts, law, humanities, sociology typically requires the funding for human resources and surveys. These are comparably less expensive as it does not require any capital investments. As far as the human resource concerns for research project managements, it is solely depends on the quality of teacher and students⁵⁰. This can be ensured through rigorous recruitment process.

The outcome of a research is measured through publication. Thus a pressure to publish is useful for the reputation of the university. A reputed research and innovation profile of a university always attracts competence intakes which help build the university brand^{51, 52}.

4.6 Publications

The publications of research outcome have many forms. The primary research outcome can be a conference poster/article which can be followed by a research article. Besides, there is short note/communication and research data article/report which can also be published. For general communication, now a day a graphical abstract has become popular. These are the abstract images created with the aid of computational software which are published on the cover page of a journal/magazine or as a featured article in newspaper. Universities today feel that increasing the number of publications cited worldwide must be a specific goal of their research strategy in order to increase their chances of improving their ranking levels. Even so, you need to strategize how to achieve this. This probably means concentration, as not all departments or research groups within departments are winners in this regard⁵³.

Established research groups with good track records may be part of the focus, but potential emerging groups may also be a focus. Strategic choices also depend on the academic and social profile of the university and the selection of the disciplines it wishes to serve as role models from a holistic perspective. Such strategic considerations are often contradictory, and identifying and planning how a university's research budget should be allocated based on its research strategy is usually a complex process. Citation and citation potential are not the only criteria to consider. Universities' contributions to the immediate and wider educational, social and business environment can also be important starting points for research strategies aimed at increasing the volume of public and private publishing. In general, the research strategy also aims to take advantage of the possibility of obtaining grants from various other external funding sources for the university.

4.6.1 Open access Journal

There are three forms of publication model, subscription, open access and hybrid. The subscription model does not require any article processing charge (APC) but reader need to pay for reading an article. The reading of the article can be done online or through hard copy of the journal. The Open Access model requires an APC to be paid once the article is approved for publication by the reviewers and the editorial board. The advantage of this process is that the reader does not require any fees to read the article. It is observed that the open access model is economically viable as pay's only the APC for the article published by the respective faculty members. Also the expenditure due to the yearly subscription from the university library can be reduced or adjusted. Open Access is a broad international movement aimed at providing free and open online access to scientific information, including publications and data. Publications are permitted if there are no economic, legal, or technical barriers to access, i.e., if anyone can read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, retrieve, or use the educational information. defined as "open access". Or within the framework of

a legal agreement. Open access is a publishing model of scholarly communication that makes research information freely available to readers, as opposed to the traditional subscription model in which readers access scholarly information by paying a subscription fee (usually through a library). Open access journals, on the other hand, often use Creative Commons (CC) licenses, making it easier for users to share, use, and build on the original work. One of the most important benefits of open access is increased visibility and reusability of scientific research results. There are also criticisms, and special attention should be paid to the quality aspect. The principles of open access are set out in the Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Scientific Knowledge (2003). This declaration has been signed by many international academic and research institutions, including all Dutch universities and research institutes.

4.6.2 Subscription Journal

Subscription-based journals typically require readers to pay for the content they read. This is the model traditionally employed in the scholarly publishing industry. Individuals or institutions must pay a subscription fee, so only those who subscribe to your journal/article can access your work. In the subscription model, copyright for published content is usually transferred to the journal, whereas in open access journals, copyright usually remains with the author. This means that in order to publish an article in a subscription-based journal, anyone wishing to use parts of the article must obtain the journal's permission. Articles are copyrighted and available only to subscribers of the particular journals. There is usually no publication fee on this basis, but some journals do charge for additional services such as English editing, extra article page or color image fee.

4.7 Ranking of Journals

Any academic publication is an outcome of the intellectual works by the scholars. The research works can be published mainly in journals and conference proceeding. Beside these, books can be published by compiling research works of relevant field which is explained in more generalized terms. On an average there are 0.3 million titles which combines both online and offline documents which are published each year. It is impossible to choose where to publish. Also there are many journals which do not continue to publish after few years. Many publisher changes the names of the journals after few volume. Over time, many journals loose there importance to the relevant fields. To solve these problems, in 2003, few companies such as Google, Thomson Reuters (Clarivate), and Elsevier have taken an initiative to indexing the journals and conferences proceedings. At presents there are many indexing data base those are active online. These data base uses intelligent software to collect metadata from other web platform. This way, over the ten years of search and cataloguing now there are few accepted indexing platform such as Scopus (Elsevier), Google Scholars, Research gate, Web of science (Clarivate) etc. The Scopus data base catalogued around 40000 journals and web of science have catalogued 15000 journals. Any researcher can follow primarily the Scopus data base and for secondary choice they can follow Web of Science data base for selecting a journal. The indexing data base provides quantitative data along with qualitative understanding. Using the data from the indexing platform, there are other web base platforms which uses the data from indexing services. For example, SCImago is a web base application which provides statistical analysis of the particular journal and publisher. The SCImago provides a qualitative analysis in terms ranking. The ranking of journal is provided in quartiles (Q1; Q2; Q3; Q4).

Title	Type	↓ SJR	H Index	Total Docs. (2021)	Total Docs. (3years)	Total Refs. (2021)	Total Cites (3years)	Citable Docs. (3years)	Cites / Doc. (2years)	Ref. / Doc. (2021)
1 Ca-A Cancer Journal for Clinicians	journal	56.204 Q1	182	41	121	4006	17959	78	186.75	97.71
2 Nature Reviews Molecular Cell Biology	journal	33.213 Q1	452	111	338	9025	13797	161	38.55	81.31
3 Quarterly Journal of Economics	journal	31.348 Q1	272	48	111	3406	2241	110	16.30	70.96

Figure 4.1 The web page image of the journal ranking by SCImago⁵⁴.

4.7.1 Scimago Journal Ranking (SJR)

“SCImago” is a research group from the “Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), University of Granada, Extremadura, Carlos III (Madrid, Spain) and Alcalá de Henares”. The institution collects information of journals and publications from website and other online sources. It is an open online platform which is visible to all. It uses the Scopus database (Elsevier B.V.) for analytical reports. The figure 4.2 shows the SCImago journal ranking (SJR) of a particular journal over the period of 2012-2020. The SJR system analyses various indicators which are shown in scientific domains. The various journals are cataloged in different subject area with 27 major. These subjects are further categorized in 309 specific sub major. The citation data is produced from 34,100 titles which includes approximately 5,000 publishers. The database publishes data on all of the 239 countries worldwide. This platform takes its name from the SCImago Journal Rank (SJR) indicator, developed by SCImago from the widely known algorithm “Google PageRank™”¹⁶.

Figure 4.2 SCImago journal ranked data for a particular journal over the period of 2012-2020¹⁶.

The SJR is a prestige indicator that ranks journals by their average prestige per article. It measures both the number of citations received by a journal and the importance or prestige of the journals where such citations come from. Thus self-citations are not measured equally with external citation. All of the journals those are ranked by SCImago is divided into four groups which is termed as four quartiles (Q). The Q1 (green) comprises the quarter of the journals with the highest values, Q2 (yellow) the second highest values, Q3 (orange) the third highest values and Q4 (red) the lowest values.

4.3 SCImago quartiles data of a particular journal over a period of 20 years.

4.7.2 H-Index

The h-index is an author-level metric that measures both publication productivity and citation impact and was originally used for individual scientists and scholars. The h-index correlates with tangible indicators of success, such as winning a Prize, receiving a research grant, or securing a post at a prestigious university. This index is based on the scientist's most cited work and the number of citations received in other publications. The index was suggested in 2005 by Jorge E. Hirsch, a physicist at The University of California San Diego, La Jolla, CA 92093, United States, as a tool for determining theoretical physicists' relative quality and is sometimes called the Hirsch index or Hirsch number.

4.7.3 Total Documents

The total documents of a journal are stored under the two categories. Cited document and not cited documents. This is a basic indicator that show the quality of the articles published in the particular journal. The editorial board must choose article carefully. The thumb rule is each article should be cited at least once even if it is self cited. This will keep the cited-non cited ratio one.

Figure 4.4 SCImago data of a particular journal for the ratio between the cited and uncited documents.

4.7.4 Total Citation vs Self Citation

The meaning of self-citation is the citations those are cited in the article publish in the same journal. The figure 4.5 shows the graphical presentation of the number of citation to the all documents published to the number of citation received from the same journal. It is a norm to keep the self-citation as low as possible.

Figure 4.5 SCImago data of a particular journal for the total citation received and total self-citation received.

4.7.5 Total Citation vs External Citation

For a journal it is expected that the article published in the journal will be cited by the external journal. It is evaluated by subtracting the number of self-citations from the total number of citations received by the journal's documents in the a period of three years.

Figure 4.6 SClmago data of a particular journal for the total citation and external citations.

4.7.6 Citation per Documents

Citation per document is the most widely appreciated indicator for a journal. This indicator counts the total number of citations received by documents from a journal and divides them by the total number of documents published in that journal. For example, if one article receives one citation, the citation per document is 1, which is termed as Impact Factor. It is to be worth mentioning that, the impact factor must be calculate by the standard agencies such as Scopus or Web of Science data base. The figure 4.7 shows the graphical representation

Figure 4.7 SCImago data of a particular journal for the citation per documents widely known as the Impact Factor.

4.7.7 International Collaboration

An article can be authored by scholars from same country, from different county and same country but different institution. All of the above are considered as collaborative works. The international collaboration is the manuscripts is authored by authors from different countries. It is believed that an international collaborative research is highly appreciated by the scholars around the world. The figure 4.8 shows the SCImago data of a particular journal for the percent of articles with international collaboration. The higher the percent, higher the SJR.

Figure 4.8 SCImago data of a particular journal for the articles with international collaboration.

4.7.8 Citable documents vs Non-citable documents

A journal should put all of the published articles online for the online search robot to read. These site collects the meta data from the journal website. Figure 4.9 shows the SCImago data of a particular journal for the citable document to the non-citable document. It is publishers practice that non-citable documents are kept as low as possible.

Figure 4.9 SClmago data of a particular journal for the citable document to the non citable document

Chapter 5

Engaging Researchers Community

5.1 Introduction

The concept of basic education is to promote learning so the students become capable to learn from the environment. This basic education is provided up to an age of 12-15 years. After the basic education, a student can be further educated up to 18 years of age. At this point a student learns as well as reasons the learning for skill base job market. Beyond the age of 18 years, the education become limited to a group of student those require competitive skills. This education is widely known as higher education which is provided in University or in in university colleges. At this point a student must possess skills and knowledge in particular field of expertise. Producing competitive candidate for the need of the industry and society research is an essential part. Engaging researcher's community such as students, teachers, alumni, industries and stakeholders can be a way forward in achieving this goal. The conference, seminars and workshops are primary concepts which allow the engagement at large scale. In this case participatory approach is widely used by the institutions⁵⁵. This chapter discusses the various ways of engaging the research community⁵⁶. This includes the process and importance of arranging an annual international seminar, Quarterly Seminar, Workshop on skill development, Guest Lecture as an addition to the regular class room teaching, and Research Fair showcasing innovation and ideas in terms of projects and models.

5.2 Annual International Seminar/Conference

Seminars and conferences are best practice in academic arena in exploring the current trends in research⁵⁷. Organizing an annual conference or seminar can be an academic calendar event so every entity in a university learns about objective⁵⁸. Once the entire university family accepts the event from heart, it will have a significant influence in developing a research culture. Only then it will be considered as their job duties.

To successfully organize an international conference or seminar, it is the leadership and the authority who should be vested significantly. This works as the fuel to do the job done by the personnel at the various stages of the organization. The major input comes from the top down manner such as the date, venue and invitees. The venue of the event should be chosen keeping two criteria in mind; one is closer to the communication hub such as airport, train stations or bus terminals another is the area around the venue should be located in academic or a quiet neighborhood. Anyway, a university campus is the best place to arrange such events which in turn provides implicit publication of the university.

5.2.1 Planning Theme and Topics

The top down approach allows a synchronized workflow. This process does not require an approval mechanism. Thus selecting theme and topic of the conference or seminar will initiate the process which can be chosen depending on the specialization of the University on any Global Agenda. The objective of such conference is engaging researcher's community in a place where they can share ideas and thought. This is critical for a topic and inviting the icons in the field. The researchers those are reputed in a field will attract more participants. Thus it is a common practice to put their profiles and abstract on a web page at the beginning of the call for papers.

5.2.2 Making Program

Once the venue, date, theme and guest are decided, the core committee require to make program, prospectus, brochure which contains all the necessary information for the volunteers and attendee. It is considered to be the second stage to be implemented. For the context of Bangladesh, It can be started early in 0900H with a tea break at 1100H followed by a lunch at 1400H. The second phase can be started at 1530H and can be continued up to 1800H. The participants, who came from are invited from other organizations or educational institutions are allotted specific time to make presentations. In between, the students are also given time to make their poster presentations.

5.2.3 Sending Invitations

Seminars and workshops are successful if many people participate. Sending out invitations to all individuals is her third step in organizing seminars and workshops. When carrying out this work, the seminar organizer is obliged to invite other persons. People are members of educational institutions and departments: administrators, students, and other employees. In addition, leaders, directors, educators, researchers and other staff from other educational institutions and organizations are invited. Members of educational institutions and departments will also communicate personally within the framework of seminars and workshops. Now, with the advent of new technologies, invitations are sent through sending messages and emails. These are faster and ensure clearer information. In some cases, we may contact you personally by phone. The main purpose of the phone is to remind the individual.

5.2.4 Assigning the Job Duties

Assigning work tasks to individuals is the fourth step that must be performed when conducting a seminar or workshop. Seminar organizers are expected to collaborate and

integrate with other members to facilitate this work effectively. Teamwork should be encouraged to perform all tasks and activities in an organized manner. Tasks are divided according to members' skills and abilities. For example, students with excellent communication and presentation skills are assigned the role of anchor. These tell the audience the task and who was invited to the talk or presentation. In other words, your main job is to convey clear information to your audience. Meanwhile, other members are involved in other tasks such as appointment schedules, venues, and refreshments. All members must have sufficient information to perform their duties properly and achieve the desired results.

5.2.5 Cultural Show

A cultural show at the end/evening of an international seminar/conference is to keep the international as well as national guest engaged. It helps to share cultural experience between nations and communities. The event consists of traditional music, dance, drama, recitation etc. which are chosen carefully for showcasing the local culture. It also show case the national sprit towards unity and love for the motherland.

5.2.6 BSMRMU International Seminar

The BSMRMU organizes international seminar on yearly basis. The international seminar allows the university to showcase its achievements to the community. This also provides a platform for teachers and students to present their research works in the form of oral and poster presentation to the wider audience. BSMRMU has organized its first international seminar in 2018 on ocean governance which was a two day seminar with 1000 participants. Among them there were 12 international speakers along with local speakers from various universities and institutions. Total 24 paper were presented. In 2019, the second International seminar was arranged on maritime development and security. This was a one day seminar with 10 international speaker along with other national speakers. Total 12 paper were presented in the seminar. Due

to the COVID-19, the third International seminar were arranged in 2022 on the Decade of Ocean Science. This was a one day seminar but with a broader aspects. For the first time, the seminar accommodated a larger number of oral presentation through parallel technical session along with plenary session. Total 24 paper was presented in a single day event. In an addition, to encourage the participation of students, 40 posters were presented in the seminar which includes all of the universities in Bangladesh who have the department of oceanography. The total participant of this seminar was around one thousand.

An international seminar is a gathering where experts from relevant subjects presents a topic of global interest. This explores the views of student on the recent scientific trends. Thus a seminar creates an environment among the teachers, researchers, stakeholders, students, policy makers and industries.

Image 5.1 Photos taken on the occasion of the BSMRMU 3rd International Seminar.

5.3 Quarterly Seminar

The quarterly seminar is mostly organized by the different Faculty such as (commerce, law, science, arts, etc.). These are mainly limited to specific community and departments among the faculty. Thus they may have smaller number of participants. The faculty seminars encourage students out of box thinking with the sharing research with teachers⁵⁹. i) encourage open discussion; Seminars and workshops differ from lectures in that the speaker does not speak to the entire audience, but is mediated by a third party. Create a conversational atmosphere where you can discuss business-related topics and hear the opinions of other participants. ii) provide different perspectives; Attend workshops and seminars to find answers to common questions.

Workshop participants can share their thoughts and ideas and gain new perspectives on topics. iii) New ideas are born. Listening to other people's ideas can help generate new ideas for your work. You will come up with ideas that you never thought of before. Sharing with others and hearing their opinions has the potential to unleash your creativity. The great thing about seminars is that participants are encouraged to ask questions and network with others to explore ways to apply what they learn. iv) Scientific meetings. Improve your skills. Seminars and workshops are a great place to learn new skills that will help you succeed in your career. Some seminars also offer hands-on training on various software programs and tools to help you reach your professional peak. v) Seminars can build relationships. In job hunting, it's more about who you know than what you know. There are many reasons to take advantage of networking opportunities whenever the opportunity arises. vi) It can encourage and motivate you. Attending seminars and learning about different topics opens up new ideas and possibilities. This will motivate you to continue your business, your studies, or any other endeavour. Teaching involves research and learning as a natural part of the process. Remember that the seminar will give you excellent support to influence, encourage and motivate you. vii) Seminar days provide a different environment. Attending seminars increases self-confidence, productivity and performance, as you can learn more effectively and efficiently in a learning environment that is different from the classroom or the workplace. viii) Seminars where you can learn about new technologies and trends from experts. You need a basic understanding of how new technology works and how it can benefit your business. You can read and research a topic, but nothing beats talking to someone face-to-face about the same topic. That's why seminars are a great opportunity to broaden your knowledge. Attendees at these events are well versed in the latest technologies and eager to share their expertise with others.

In addition, students are provided with the opportunity to give lectures and lectures in one-day seminars. Write a research paper or give a presentation using PowerPoint

slides. Additionally, interacting with individuals inside and outside your organization can go a long way in improving your public speaking skills. In this way, students are taught that they need to interact with other people and overcome their introversion in order to improve their career prospects. Improving public speaking skills enhances learning and inspires thinking to achieve educational goals. Students will be awarded a certificate for successful completion of the assignment. This helps students succeed academically and meet the expectations of their teachers and supervisors.

5.3.1 BSMRMU Quarterly Seminar

There are seven faculties at BSMRMU out of which five faculties have program. These faculties are responsible to organize national level seminar once in a year. These faculties are responsible to organize seminar at a limited scale for the benefits of its students. These are known as quarterly seminar. In these seminars, most of the experts/speakers are from the relevant fields of the particular department of the faculty. The major emphases are given to the thought that this will discuss the current trends in the particular field. For example, the faculty of Earth and Ocean Science arranges a seminar on Marine Pollution. The department may invite one or two individual experts from abroad. The average number of participant varies between 100-150, depending on the number of students in the respected faculty.

Image 5.2 Photos from the Quarterly seminar arranged by the Faculty.

Image 5.3 Quarterly seminar arranged by the Faculty at BSMRMU.

5.4 Workshop

It is clear that some subjects and lesson plans are complex. Students are overwhelmed with numerous problems and challenges. These are painful to them and they strive to provide solutions in a way that satisfies them. Problems and difficult situations usually lead to obstacles in understanding concepts and achieving educational goals. By organizing workshops around specific topics and concepts, students can gain a deeper understanding of academic concepts and clear their doubts. As a result, they study well and get good grades. Students are provided with opportunities to give lectures and talks. Write a research paper or give a presentation using PowerPoint slides. In this way, you can improve your communication and dialogue skills. Thus, an understanding of the meaning and importance of seminars and workshops is gained when they provide answers to questions and help broaden learning. Workshop organizers imitate leaders, directors, educators, researchers, and other staff of other institutions and organizations on specific topics. They give presentations and speeches on topics and concepts for which seminars and workshops are organized. We will use different types of reading materials and give PowerPoint presentations. Their goal is to encourage learning and remove all doubts. By implementing effective communication processes, you can expand your learning in modern, scientific and innovative ways. Information will also be collected on how to promote the enhancement of the entire educational system. Once information is collected, it should be put into practice in an organized and disciplined manner. Therefore, when a workshop facilitates interaction with individuals from other organizations and educational institutions, the purpose and importance of the workshop are well understood.

Image 5.4 shows the various interactive sessions during workshop arranged by the research project. The remarks of the resource person on his experience after the five days' workshop is as follows.

Bangladesh's higher education system requires significant improvements to meet local and global demand. One of the significant challenges confronting Bangladesh's tertiary education system is "quality of teaching and research conditions." Improving quality was also identified as a key cross-cutting strategic goal of Bangladesh Higher Education reform frameworks. Higher education institutions in Bangladesh must make provisions to ensure the quality of research and education.

As a result, Higher Education Institutions must develop a strategic vision for research and publication. This Institutional Annual Research Initiative (IARI) will assist Higher Education Institutions such as BSMRMU and its academics in preparing and publishing world-class research papers in prestigious journals. Through research and scholarly activities, the institution will not only demonstrate its strong commitment to research activities. Still, it will also assist institutions in raising their profile and increasing their chances of being included in the QS University Ranking system.

This joint collaborative research will be conducted by BSMRMU and CBER, London, UK. While the annual research initiative recognizes and supports the significance of a broad range of significant research, scholarly activities, and creative works; it also identifies some fundamental thematic and hallmark areas for improvement. These should be determined through extensive consultations and selected based on their uniqueness, their potential to draw on strengths from across the BSMRMU that combine teaching, research, scholarly activities and creative works, public service activities, and their relevance to national and international priorities in today's rapidly transforming society. This annual initiative must be considered an integral part of the University's Strategic Research Plan. This initiative will support the institution in taking specific research-related activities to foster research and collaboration.

Image 5.4 Workshops organized at BSMRMU

5.5 Guest Lecture

It is often difficult to initiate the thought process among the students on a particular topic during the academic lecture sessions. Moreover, the academic lectures are limited by the syllabus and semester finals. Thus the introduction to a new topic is often difficult. This has an adverse effect on the student as they do not feel interest in the subject matter. Making the topic interesting to a student is an art. Guest lectures are the solution to the problem. The guest lectures are considered as an add-on to the regular academic activities. An expert from the subject may trigger the interest in students. The expert can be chosen from the academia as well as from the industry. An expert (the guest) is a reputed figure who has achieved excellence in the particular field. This envisioned the student as his/her future prospects. BSMRMU organizes guest lecture time to time depending on the requirements.

Image 5.5 Guest speech arranged by BSMRMU

5.6 Research Fair/Festival

Most young graduates lack self-confidence and lack verbal fluency. Many students from rural and suburban areas have excellent academic performance and industrial skills, but lack the ability to express themselves. This small but big drawback often hinders student performance during on-campus internships. Speaking about a research topic in front of an assembled audience at an exposition or festival gives students confidence and prepares them especially for interviews and group discussions.

Fairs/Festivals provide an opportunity to connect with other students in their respective fields, especially those from different institutes/departments. By discussing topics related to the subject in question, students typically learn up-to-date information and new skills related to the subject in question. Because of their genuine interest in familiarizing themselves with and learning about the subject, students study

the subject under expert guidance and reach conclusions through careful investigation, experimentation, and simulation. The fair brings together students, faculty, and alumni from various educational institutions. Meeting new people gives students guidance and solutions to common problems. Making new friends not only encourages new ways of thinking and learning, it can also open up new opportunities. After the fair, these networking chains will help students further develop their professional life.

Another aspect of research fairs/festivals is encouragement and motivation. Talking and learning about new topics encourages students to explore new areas related to the topic. Students feel motivated to explore and learn new things. With proper guidance from teachers and experts, students can feel motivated to publish their own research journal and make a significant contribution to the field of education. Research fairs provide a different environment than a classroom. It is a unique learning environment that is different from the classroom. Students can learn more effectively and efficiently. Far from textbooks and academic curricula, students research and learn independently, increasing their self-confidence, sense of accomplishment and productivity.

Image 5.6 BSMRMU organizes research fair/festival/poster presentation

Image 5.7 BSMRMU organizes research fair/festival/poster presentation

Image 5.8 Chittagong University and Dhaka University organizes research fair/festival/poster presentation

Image 5.9 Dhaka University recognizes the best poster presentation awards through handing over crest and certificated in the first research fair/festival/poster presentation.

Chapter 6

Training and Development of Researchers

6.1 Introduction

Training and development is an important activity that increases the performance of researchers in an educational institute like university. It is a building block which enhances the growth and success of the university in global ranking⁶⁰. It is a process of investment which keeps and in many cases transforms the human in to efficient resources⁶¹. For a researchers, training refers to bridging the gap between the current performance and the standard desired performance. A definition from Somasundaram, Usha Valli, and T. Egan et. al. 2004 states that "an educational process that involves the sharpening of skills, concepts, changing of attitude and gaining of more knowledge to enhance the performance of employees"⁶². Thus the concept of training is considered as the activity of the institution towards the employee. The process of training is thought to be a changing mechanism so the employee is enhanced in attitude or increasing his or her skills and knowledge⁶³. The working capacity and capability of an employee has a relationship with the performance of the institution directly. To ensure the performance of the institution, the training program has become a routine work⁶⁴. This chapter describes the importance and role of training and development of a researcher through job satisfaction, national and international collaboration. This also includes creating a culture of continuous development through various means such as establishing a research center and appointing a research chair to guide and boost the enthusiasm.

6.2. Job Satisfaction

The job satisfaction is a relative term. It is a state of mental activity of the human which keep one satisfies and others are not though the environment is identical for both. Out of many elements which increase the job satisfaction, training is considered as the most effective. It has two major components, one, the employee is released form the regular duty with an extra honorarium and second it adds a value to the skill set which is used in the carrier. An international visit during the training is an addition to the satisfaction. Thus it is said to be an investment for the employee as well as for the institution⁶⁵. These initiatives tend to bring employees closer together, strengthen culture, and help individual team members identify new partners, collaborators, mentors and subject-matter experts within the institution. The university is a great place for teaching and research. The major work force is the students, teachers and the co-workers. But a large number of the work force does not involve in research. Many faculty members remain in teaching only while limited of them move toward more research oriented carrier. Most of the undergraduate students end up their degree with a project which ends with a report. Thus siphoning the significant amount of workforce toward the research requires satisfaction and retention mechanism.

6.3 Creating Culture

With many university staff urgently needing to participate in research, it is important to foster a learning culture at research institutions where expectations are clear from the outset and the interests of researchers and institutions are shared. . It is also important to be able to refer to successful cases within the university and act accordingly. To ensure their success, it is important to have a plan for transferring knowledge back into the workplace. Staff can be encouraged to immediately put into practice the most important things they learn, and consistent approaches to training and development can create a common language and framework across the university. can. By sending employees to a (public) open enrollment program where they can network with peers

across various institutions and industries, they can test their ideas in a safe environment and bring back ideas and best practices to the organization. A forum is provided to discuss the practice. You should be encouraged to apply these new ideas to your workplace immediately and share ideas with your internal teams. One way he does that is by hosting lunches and encouraging employees to learn. Here you can present important ideas to your teammates. This also aids in knowledge transfer as it strengthens the learning culture and helps create a common language and framework for the team. Ultimately, your greatest asset is your researcher. As you improve your resources, you must update your individual skills, improve your team, and equip your team with the knowledge they need to stay competitive and do their best work. In this increasingly competitive global work environment, educational institutions that invest in employee training and development will improve in the global university ranking.

6.4 National Collaboration

Co-operation between national institutes has become new trend in the competitive world. It is difficult to facilitate researchers with individual resources while the resources are limited. Co-operation between national institutes can be of great solution to this problem⁶⁶. At national level, the institutes have common funding agencies. Which means the resources and facilities can be de centralized. Depending of the human resources and locations, various lab and research centers can be place at different universities. To materialize the idea of National collaboration, it requires forming research groups headed by senior researchers. To enhance cooperation between researchers from different institutes/groups it requires signing memorandum of understanding (MoU) ⁶⁷. This clarifies the mechanism of the relationship such as authorship, supervisor, fund transfer, usages of facilities, access to institution etc.

A national scale policy can guide the formation and execution of the proposed collaboration. For example, each group may consist of five researchers (faculty (1),

students (3)) under the leadership of one prominent scientist. The group may include one adjunct professor/expert. The research group must be unique in terms of the fields. Thus the funding can be arranged from the various field of the research⁶⁸. The research groups can be formed covering a wide spectrum of specializations as required by the community and country. The research groups can have different name to visualize their field of research such as biological, genetic, plants, food, fish, fuel etc. In addition to publishing papers in ranked journals, the research groups are expected to work on projects that benefit the local community as well.

Image 6.1 Team from BSMRMU visits Bangladesh Oceanographic Research Institutes, Cox Bazar.

6.5 International Collaboration

Collaboration is a common word among the various institutions both in industry and academia. There are two way of development, one is competitive and another is collaborative. It was believed that a collaborative environment is healthier than a competitive environment in terms of development. It is very relative to the present status of rapid communication and exchange of data through internet. An international level of collaboration means two institutions from two separate country is in an agreement to work and share knowledge. The impact of international collaboration is huge in terms of building a world class university. Without exchange one will not understand its strength and weakness. Setting the policy for international collaboration is another critical task. It requires the input form the regulating body and the government. This has become easy for Bangladesh with its neighboring countries through South Asian Regional Co-operation (SARC) set by the government. Thus universities can use the same policy to work together. The collaboration is considered as the prime index of a university in achieving world reputation. The international collaboration can be ensured in various ways such as signing MoU with relevant institutions, forming an International Advisory Board under office of International Relation and moreover connecting researchers through exposor visits. The idea behind the collaboration is to improve the quality of the university both in the social and academic⁶⁹. Once the international collaboration is set it become even critical to keep the relation fruitful. This can be kept in pace through quarterly meeting. To reduce the hassle of international travel online meeting platform can be used. In the online meeting we can introduce teachers, admin and student which would be difficult for a physical visit. This may be, out of four, three can be done online, and one can be physical visit. These meeting should be maintained through international relation department routinely. These meetings can be arranged during yearly international conference or seminar where one or two sessions can be kept for international

collaborative events. The international collaboration meeting includes the agenda on exchange students and young teachers, exchange of lab sample and material etc.

The International collaboration can be focused on

- Study of oceanography on Indian ocean.
- Study of Marine biotechnology on Indian Ocean.
- Orientation of young faculty of BSMRMU in Goa University.
- Joint curriculum committee for Oceanography and Marine Biotechnology
- Capacity building of BSMRMU through academic research
- Human resource development through joint education program
- Signing of MoU in near future.

In terms of Faculty assistance it may cover the following courses:

- Physical oceanography· Chemical oceanography
- Marine biogeochemistry· Marine geology
- Marine ecology and ocean productivity · Coastal morphology and processes
- Satellite oceanography · Marine ecosystem modeling
- Numerical techniques for ocean modeling · Acoustic oceanography
- Geophysical fluid dynamics · Meteorology and ocean forecasting
- Marine microbiology
- 4th year (UG) student visit including short courses followed by ship visit.
- Internship and ocean research of M.S and PhD students.
- Inclusion of Faculty members of BSMRMU in short expedition programme as a gesture of
- friendship.
- Participation of researchers, faculty members and student in each other's seminar and major oceanographic events.
- Sharing library and online resource facilities.

- Sponsoring PhD Students
- Assistance in setting up oceanographic laboratories. (consultancy, equipment and samples)
- Training of young faculty members on attachment system.

Image 6.2 Team from BSMRMU visits various labs at National Institute of Oceanography Goa, India.

Image 6.3 Team from BSMRMU visits various labs at University of Goa, India.

Image 6.4 Team from BSMRMU visits Arctic Ice labs at National Centre for Polar and Ocean Research, Goa, India.

6.6 Scientific Chair

In recent years, research chairs have played an important role in academic research, especially in top universities. This is because the research chair aims to bring together the efforts of the university, including all its experience and knowledge in scientific research, within the framework of a broader movement towards the betterment of society. The role of the research chair is realizing the university's goals. This is to promote the concept of research chairs among faculty members and individuals in society, strengthen participants' awareness of the importance of research chairs and their contribution to the university and society.

A Chair is an academic honor bestowed on scientists in recognition of achievements in their field of study or their potential to contribute to an area of study which is withhold by the university policy⁷⁰. To operate a Research Chair such as this require funds. It can be obtained from external sources such as alumni, industry and collaborators⁷¹. In many universities it is termed as Scientific Chairs which is similar. These are aimed at enhancing the recruitment, retention and support of top talent who work to advance the strategic interests of the university and, in particular, to advance their knowledge with the aim of becoming a world-class university. Academic Chairs are responsible for directing research and academic activities in various fields throughout the University and have made significant contributions to the academic and research community. A Research Chair or Scientific Chair program may be part of a university's strategy to become a respected R&D university by attracting and retaining the most academically successful and promising talent⁷². The status and amenities of a Research/Scientific Chairs can be set by the university administration and it has to be a Professor of outstanding research carrier.

6.7 Research Centre

Research centers are the origin of innovation in this globalized community. The performance of an institution in research is entangled with its development and social reputation. It ensures the growth of the institution on the base of knowledge and innovation⁷³. The pursuit of knowledge is a fundamental principle of research. The quality of research output directly affects the quality of teaching and learning in the classroom, benefiting students, society and the country. Promoting research in developing countries like Bangladesh will help the country emerge as a repository of knowledge on the international stage⁷⁴. Our education system faces many limitations and challenges, quality research being one of them. With the exception of a few well-known research institutes, most research institutes present a bleak picture in terms of research quality and quantity. Many institutions do not have mandatory research goals for their individual departments, and most lack the appropriate systems and infrastructure for quality research. Lack of a conducive academic environment, inadequate libraries, laboratories and facilities, inadequate infrastructure, lack of funding, and faculty shortages are some of the factors contributing to the bleak state of research in Indian academic institutions. It is widely recognized that academic research has made a significant contribution to finding solutions to many of the problems facing society and industry. There are several examples of industries turning to scientists for solutions to important problems.

The need to share knowledge between research institutes and industry is becoming increasingly apparent. As the interdisciplinary field has grown in importance, it has created inter-organizational cooperation and the sharing of knowledge. In many cases, it is the industry that ultimately benefits. This study provides basic information that can be used for planning and political decision-making. It goes without saying that academic research is an integral part of world development. At this time, it is important

to develop an integrated research mechanism in the higher education system. The system should strive for excellence in both research and teaching.

The research center can be an alternative to the faculty as it is more focused on research rather than teaching. The aim of the research center is to acquire funds and use them efficiently to produce output. The output will in turn influence the stakeholders to fund and the cycle goes on. An international outlook of the research center is important for its reputation and well recognition. Hence the administration must ensure the supply and facilitate the smooth operation of the center. Managing fund, recruiting researchers, manages logistics are the few critical which needed to be done on time. Managing projects has become a never ending task for a research center. Worldwide the project distribution has become critical day by day. Besides all this, a research center also arranges conference, workshop, and poster presentation to showcase the output.

The success of the research center can be summarized in two indexes, funds and publications⁷⁵. A patent followed by technology transfer is the ultimate achievement of a center. This is the best way to attract industry and stakeholder. Besides, the center can use the funds from the university at the initial stage which is known as incubation stage. Consultancy services can also be an opportunity for the center to use its human resources which does not require any capital investment.

Chapter 7

Roadmap for BSMRMU

7.1 Introduction

There are thirty thousand universities or similar status institutions those are producing graduates for the employment sector around the world. But not all of them are equally serving the country. To provide a standard service, in 2004, few agencies and universities have initiated a process of collecting data. Accumulating the data from the universities, it was found that there can be few indices which can be used for making a standard university. At least it can provide a guide to the excellence. Thus the concept of world class university emerged. It is usually considered that these universities will be competitive in adding to the world knowledge. These produce skilled human resources with competitive leadership quality. Now a day's many countries are taking national initiatives to build at least one world class university in each region. But in the context of the higher education, it becomes expensive. But they had to earn the ability to produce world class graduates to run the society and the country. As such, a Roadmap to become a World-Class University is a common agenda among the university leadership.

To design a roadmap, we must find answer to the following questions.

- How to define a world class university?
- Is it possible to convert a local university to a world class university?
- What are the set targets?

To define a world class university, we can chose any one out of the three ranking system QS, THE and ARWU. Once we set the definition we can proceed onto the second question. Every university is local by its inception. To understand the potential of a local university, we must analyze the relative data of these universities. For

example, Bangladesh has around 200 universities. But we do not have any mechanism to guide them toward world class university criteria. We must do that and from the analysis we can decide which university to select for the purpose. It is not necessary to have very old or young university for the selection.

To answer the third question, we need to see the target set by the three ranking system which was the answer to the first question. Each of the system has their own targets. Once we chose the ranking system, the targets are automatically set by the agencies. There are few common indices in which a university needs to excel, quality faculty members, competent students, adequate facilities, cultural diversity, environment and funds.

The vision, mission and goal of the BSMRMU is state as found in the university web site www.bsrmu.edu.bd. The vision of BSMRMU is “promoting and creating a learning environment for higher maritime education with excellence, through state of the art facilities and gadgets, competent faculty and staff, expanded frontier of research based knowledge and international standards supportive of the new horizons in diverse fields”.

The mission of BSMRMU is “to provide quality education based on state of the art technological support responsive to the emerging challenges at home and abroad”.

The goal of BSMRMU is “to achieve sustainable development and progress of the university through mutual cooperation with other related universities/ institutions. Continue to upgrade educational services and facilities responsive to the demands and requirements of the nation. Bring all types of marine professionals on a common platform to share knowledge and perform research and development works for the advancement of country's maritime sector”. This chapter proposes a roadmap to address the vision, mission and goal of BSMRMU.

7.2 Phase-I Accreditation

The term Accreditation is a measure of quality of the program. Accreditation is a review process to determine if educational programs meet defined standards of quality. There are national accreditation body such as a) IEB- Board of Accreditation for Engineering and Technical Education (BAETE), and b) Bangladesh Accreditation Council (BAC). There are international accreditation body such as Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology, Inc (ABET), North Charles St., Baltimore, Maryland (MD), USA which is a nonprofit, non-governmental organization with ISO 9001:2015 certification.

To have a drive towards the excellence at BSMRMU, one needs to be ambitious. Since 2015, BSMRMU has established its reputation as a specialized university. The university has succeeded in achieving wide acceptance to the community in terms of strong academic reputation.

Thus as a part of the roadmap, accreditation of programs are of first priority. Starting with national accreditation followed by international accreditation will make the post-secondary institutions to internationally accepted higher educational standards.

7.3 Phase-I Rating

The rating of a program provides the glimpse of the international standard at a glance. The stars are placed closed to the program flyer which helps students to understand the global recognition. The Stars rating system from QS provides a detailed look at an institution which enables identify which universities are the best in the specific topics. This includes the information like program strength, facilities, graduate employability, social responsibility, inclusiveness, and more. The rating is shown in terms of stars (1-5). The rating is a paid service thus planning for rating service requires careful attention.

7.4 Phase-I Reward

Encouraging researcher to do more always requires drive both from the institutions and from the peers. Prizes are the means to achieve that. There may be various forms of prizes. Few of them are suggested below.

- Journals publication (a basic initiative to boost the number of publication);
- Article published in ISI/sci/sciE/scopus/pubmed indexed journals;
- Monthly research prize (for teachers/students);
- Innovative research prize open to all in a country
- Yearly citation/impact factor;
- Patent Prize;
- Book or book chapter writing prize;

The prize can be in monetary or any recognition from institution which adds a value to the researcher's contribution. Paying the article processing charge can also be a good initiative.

7.5 Phase-II Global Ranking

To begin with, improving in the Webometrics Ranking system can be a good initiative which uses the university's web presence, web access, and visibility. This requires to develop the website and overall online activities of the university. Once the university ranking starts to improve in this database, the following can be followed. At the beginning the Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU) can be focused for Asian university ranking. The ARWU focuses mainly on the research output thus it can be achievable with a drive in research. The Time Higher Education (THE), and Quacquarelli Symonds (QS) World University Rankings, both publish the university rankings categorizing global overall ranking, subject ranking and regional ranking.

7.6 Key Actions

Action-1: To foster an institutional culture of research excellence that could aid the institution's eventual inclusion in world University rating lists as a reputable institution. Maritime University's core business is teaching and research. BSMRMU must continue supporting researchers and building the Institutional workforce to meet future demands.

Action-2: Increase the capacity of research staff by investing in initiatives that promote research competency, leadership, and collaboration.

Action-3: Maintain a balance between admin work, academic work and research time.

Action-4: promote research leadership and culture throughout the conference and seminar.

Action-5: To develop and construct Institutional researchers for international renown and success Effective research almost always involves collaboration, whether within academic fields, between universities, or between universities and the public or private sector. Outstanding research innovation frequently occurs at intersections or overlapping various areas or research groups. Collaboration in research can also give flow-on benefits to teaching and positively contribute to the profile of an institution of higher education and its faculty.

Action-6: Boost the effectiveness of collaborative efforts by providing rewards and encouragement for those who work together.

Action-7: Engage stakeholders and end-users in the research process through a research engagement strategy.

Action-8: Provide academics with a way to track and report on their engagement activities as part of the Professional Development Review (PDR) or Annual confidential report (ACR) process.

Action-9: To enable academics and researchers to engage with the larger community and have a proven local, national, and global impact.

Action-10: The institution should empower academic and research employees to engage in collaborative research with various stakeholder groups and international institutions. Look for locally and internationally funded research projects. Identify the areas of collaborative research with International Higher Education Institutions.

Action-11: locate locally and internationally funded research projects.

Action-12: To Create an elite research workforce and culture through continuous training and development.

Action-13: The success of academic endeavors and research projects depends on ongoing professional growth. Every team member should have access to a good training programme covering general and specialized research fields. The availability of high-quality research infrastructure is critical in determining the caliber of the academic work produced. Researchers need access to the appropriate technology, research tools, administrative procedures, and human resources to solve complicated challenges effectively. Infrastructure is the central pillar of any high-quality research environment, serving as the support system for cutting-edge research.

Action-14: Identify the training needs and build specific generic Training for Researchers (GTR). The initiative will organize several training workshops that will provide practical knowledge in preparing and publishing in indexed journals and conference proceedings **Action-15:** To create several Special Interest Groups (SIG) to undertake a specialist research project. The initiative will take and recommend further areas of focus to ensure the above objectives are met

Action-16: Academic staff will strive to produce one research publication per year either in indexed Journals (SCOPUS or other similar types) or in the indexed conference proceedings

Action-17: To increase the number of research papers for each grant cycle, it is important to publish project report/thesis submitted by the undergraduate and graduate students.

Action-18: Research-active staff members will be excused from admin and teaching for predetermined periods to complete research projects.

Action-19: Training on Generic Research programme for the academic staff to increase research competencies.

Action-20: Partnerships with schools to be formed to include collaborative research work.

Action-21: Annual individual research plans should be submitted by academic staff.

Action-22: Academic staff will seek to establish collaborative relationships with research partners at other higher education institutions, focusing on expanding the university's international networks.

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